

old TN1 rice plants for 24 h oviposition, in 5 replications. Number of eggs was adjusted to test 10, 20, or 40 per plant. *A. longipennis* starved for 24 h were introduced individually into the cages. The number of eggs consumed was recorded daily for 3 d.

A. longipennis preferred eggs of LF

and green hairy caterpillar (see table). By the second day, the crickets had consumed almost all the eggs of the LF and green hairy caterpillar but ate only about one-fourth of the green horned caterpillar eggs by the third day. In general, predation on LF and hairy caterpillar eggs was about three times

higher than predation on green horned caterpillar eggs. (The eggs of green horned caterpillar are larger than those of the other species tested.)

These results show that *A. longipennis* is capable of making a significant impact on eggs of two species of rice pests. □

Effect of insecticide application at different growth stages on rice yield components and rice straw

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The field experiment with 10 treatments (see table) was laid out in a randomized block design with 4 replications during summer and wet seasons 1986. Yellow

stem borer (YSB) and leaf roller (LR) were the dominant insect pests during the study. Deadhearts and whiteheads percentages were recorded for YSB and percentage of infested leaves for LR.

Grains from 10 individual selected panicles were counted at maturity and 1,000-grain wt determined separately for each treatment. Grain yield was recorded from the net plot area, straw yield was recorded separately for each treatment. Straw yield loss (t/ha and %) was determined by deducting yield with treatment from yield with maximum

protection.

Insecticide significantly influenced pest incidence, rice yield components, and straw yield. The plot with maximum protection had the lowest % deadhearts, whiteheads, and LR infested leaves, with correspondingly higher grains/panicle, 1,000-grain weight, grain yield, and straw yield. Maximum protection except at ripening had the lowest straw yield loss. Increased yields appear to be due to suppression of insect pests, not to fertilizer effects of carbofuran. □

Yield components and straw yield of rice with insecticide applications at different growth stages.^a Navsari, India, 1986 summer and wet season.

Treatment ^b	Deadhearts (%)	Whiteheads (%)	Leaves infested with LR (%)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Straw loss	
								t/ha	%
Maximum protection	3.05 (09.30)	2.60 (06.76)	2.18 (04.75)	289.0	16.0	8.9	8.7	–	–
Maximum protection except seedbed	3.34 (11.16)	2.87 (08.24)	2.41 (05.81)	252.8	15.2	8.1	7.8	0.9	11.5
Maximum protection except vegetative stage	3.97 (15.76)	2.95 (08.70)	3.09 (09.55)	249.6	14.4	6.7	6.7	2.0	29.9
Maximum protection except reproductive stage	3.96 (15.68)	3.13 (09.80)	2.49 (06.20)	237.2	15.2	7.0	7.1	1.6	22.5
Maximum protection except ripening stage	3.19 (10.18)	2.79 (07.78)	2.30 (05.29)	278.9	16.0	8.6	8.4	0.3	3.6
Seedbed protection	4.97 (24.70)	3.62 (13.10)	3.31 (10.96)	225.0	14.4	5.9	6.1	2.6	42.6
Vegetative stage protection	4.18 (17.47)	3.46 (11.97)	2.58 (06.66)	225.0	15.2	6.8	6.7	2.0	29.9
Reproductive stage protection	4.51 (20.34)	3.00 (09.00)	3.22 (10.37)	231.0	15.2	6.6	6.6	2.1	31.8
Ripening stage protection	5.37 (28.84)	3.31 (11.36)	3.48 (12.11)	207.4	14.4	6.0	6.2	2.5	40.3
Control (no protection)	6.20 (38.44)	3.81 (14.52)	3.86 (14.90)	196.0	13.7	5.8	5.8	2.9	50.0
LSD (0.05)	0.54	0.03	0.24	9.0	0.6	0.9	0.4	–	–
CV (%)	18.90	0.86	13.02	4.5	1.1	10.0	3.4	–	–

^aPooled mean for 1986 summer and wet season. Figures in parentheses are retransformed values in squares. ^bMaximum protection = seedbed protection: carbofuran 3 G at 0.5 kg ai/ha 5 d before transplanting; vegetative stage protection: foliar spray of monocrotophos 36 WSC at 0.036% at 5 and 25 d after transplanting (DT), carbofuran 3 G at 1.0 kg ai/ha at 15 DT, and foliar spray of fenitrothion 50 EC at 0.05% at 35 DT; reproductive stage protection: foliar spray of monocrotophos 36 WSC at 0.036% at panicle initiation and flowering; ripening stage protection: foliar spray of monocrotophos 36 WSC at 0.036% at soft dough stage.